

Work Package 1 – Shared modelling framework and learnings

Task 1.5- Framework for socio-economic assessment

D1.2 – Description of scientific methods

Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis

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Acronyms and abbreviations

ABBREVIATIONS	Description
EU	European Union
FWP	Fair wage potential
GHG	Greenhouse emissions
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LMC	Levelized material cost
MCDA	Multi-criteria decision analysis
SMAA	Stochastic multi-attribute analysis
TEA	Techno-economic assessment

Executive summary

This task consists of coordinating a consistent implementation of socio-economic assessment within the ALIGNED project. It consists of three building blocks: (i) economic evaluation (techno-economic assessment), social impact assessment (social indicator model), and (iii) multi-criteria decision analysis. In this particular description, the developer focuses on the stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis method based on Prado and Heijungs (2018).

It first sets the basis for assessing the sustainability (economic, environmental, and social dimensions) of technologies, products, or projects through the provided tools and tutorials that can be used by partners and general practitioners. It will then facilitate its application to the case studies in the bio-based sector by providing specific guidelines for modeling and analyzing the economic feasibility.

1. The need for sustainability in the bio-based sectors

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development expresses a dedication to realize sustainable development across economic, social, and environmental domains in a harmonized and cohesive manner (United Nations, 2015). Hence, the European Commission introduced the strategy "European Green Deal". This initiative aims to transform the European Union (EU)

into a society that is both fair and prosperous, characterized by a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy (European Commission, 2019). In addition to governmental policies and environmental regulations, sustainability is also stimulated by customer's demand and increasing societal and environmental awareness (Leal-Millan et al., 2018). Consequently, companies are faced with the challenge of adopting new strategies, products, and technologies that prioritize sustainability.

Achieving sustainability is closely tied to the implementation of existing and novel innovative technologies and products, ideally with reduced environmental impacts and positive social and economic outcomes. In a world of population growth and increasing environmental challenges (e.g. climate change), the bioeconomy is gaining prominence as it provides an avenue to harmonize economic expansion with environmentally responsible practices, presenting the prospect of a low-carbon economy and the creation of new jobs (Eickhout, 2012). The advancement of the bioeconomy is a key element of the 2020 strategy (Fritsche and Iriarte, 2014). Consequently, the European Commission formulated the Bioeconomy Strategy in 2012 to serve as a guide for research and innovation agendas (European Commission, 2012). An updated version of this strategy was released in 2018, aligning more effectively with contemporary policy priorities (European Commission, 2018).

The development of new or enhanced industrial processes is essential for converting biomass into various energy applications and other products. However, the utilization of organic matter (i.e., biomass) for food, feed, biobased products, and bioenergy carries potential negative impacts, such as land use changes due to deforestation and unsustainable farming practices, as well as increased water use. Consequently, it is crucial to measure and monitor these sustainability-related impacts, preferably already during the developmental phase of new biobased technologies (Van Schoubroeck et al., 2018).

2. Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis

To evaluate and compare the sustainability of products, processes, or technologies, three domains are essential to be covered: economic, environmental, and social. To do so, multiple methods have been developed. To name a few of them: techno-economic assessment (TEA) for the economic feasibility, social indicator quantification for the social part, and life cycle assessment (LCA) for the environmental part. The usual approach is to conduct these assessments separately and compare the results among the alternatives. This approach is quite straightforward when dealing with single indicators.

However, once the assessments are based on multiple indicators, interpretation becomes challenging, usually ending up with no clear single best alternative (Laurin et al., 2016). For instance, in LCA, one can choose multiple indicators to evaluate the products. In this case, the user has no other choice than to compare alternatives side by side across all environmental indicators (Prado and Heijungs, 2018). However, multiple indicators assessment can lead to subjectivity/bias when determining the most preferable alternative (Hertwich and Hammitt, 2001).

Hence, studies often focus only on a single environmental indicator (e.g. carbon footprint), leaving the user to interpret multiple environmental factors without clear guidance or to come up with a single score using either random or standard weight factors (Prado and Heijungs, 2018). Although quantifying different environmental impacts provides valuable insights, the complexity of the results makes it difficult to make profound decisions.

To resolve these challenges, it is advised to use multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), which considers mutual differences. MCDA is a decision-supporting method addressing

complex problems with high uncertainties, conflicting goals, different forms of information, and different interests and viewpoints (Wang et al., 2009).

To better balance different impact categories and view them more objectively, the stochastic multi-attribute analysis (SMAA) has been introduced by Prado-Lopez et al. (2014). It uses internal normalization and sets the weights randomly, without giving special preference to any specific category. Van Schoubroeck et al. (2021) extended the idea of SMAA by applying it to all dimensions of sustainability and introduced the option of implementing weighting schemes. In this case, the guideline of Prado-Lopez and Heijungs (2018) and the study of Van Schoubroeck et al. (2021) will be used to create a **stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis** for different indicators within all three domains of sustainability.

3. Guide to use the Excel file tool ‘ALINGED-T1.5_Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis_V2’

To conduct a stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis, the University of Antwerp (ANTW) provides an Excel file tool named ‘ALINGED-T1.5_Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis_V2’. It consists of the following worksheets:

- **ReadMe**
- **Input parameters & results**
- **Products indicator value (h)**
- **Pairwise difference (d)**
- **Thresholds**
- **Outranking score (theta)**
- **Net flows (π)**
- **Weights (w)**
- **Overall score (z) and rank (R)**

This guide provides an explanatory tutorial on how to conduct a stochastic MCDA based on the Prado and Heijungs (2018).

Before using the ‘stochastic MCDA’, the user is advised to pay attention to the legend, which indicates which values need to be (i) inserted (green), (ii) are calculated automatically (white), or (iii) represent the results (blue), illustrated in **Figure 1**:

LEGEND (color indication)
Value to be inserted by the user
Value calculated automatically
Results

Figure 1: Colour-based legend.

3.1 ReadMe

This sheet provides a general overview of all worksheets and their purposes within the Excel file ‘ALINGED-T1.5_Stochastic multi-criteria decision analysis_V2’. Moreover, it describes the utilization of the different sources within the datasheets.

3.2 Input parameters & results

Inputs:

The worksheet ‘Input parameters & results’ represents the starting point of the calculation method. To illustrate how the stochastic MCDA works, a hypothetical comparative case study is used, consisting of 4 alternatives (e.g. products A, B, C, and D) and 3 indicators (greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), levelized material cost (LMC), and fair wage potential (FWP)) representing one indicator per sustainability pillar. Note that the indicators can be from the same domain (e.g. environmental indicators) or from different domains (e.g. economic, environmental, and social), and can be extended to even more indicators.

Action required: First, the user needs to insert the mean values (*mean*) and the standard deviations (*sigma*), representing the uncertainty, for each product’s indicator to run a randomized Monte Carlo simulation.

Let’s assume that we are comparing the GHG emissions for 4 different products (A, B, C, and D) that have the same functionality (e.g. different chairs but the same functionality = seating). Each product has different GHG emissions and different uncertainty levels of the outcome. The same applies to the indicators LMC and FWP, see **Table 1**.

Table 1: Mean value and standard deviation of indicators GHG, LMC, and FWP for products A, B, C, and D.

Indicators	Abbr.	Unit	Product A		Product B		Product C		Product D	
			mean_A	sigma_A	mean_B	sigma_B	mean_C	sigma_C	mean_D	sigma_D
Greenhouse gas emissions	GHG	(kg CO2-eq.)	8.58	0.86	4.79	0.48	8.60	0.86	4.81	0.48
Levelized material cost	LMC	(EUR/unit)	69.36	6.94	55.12	5.51	73.17	7.32	58.09	5.81
Fair wage potential	FWP	Unitless	-1.95	0.20	-1.95	0.20	-1.87	0.19	-1.87	0.19

Weighting scheme

As the user deals with different pillars of sustainability at the same time, the indicators need to be weighted according to the importance that is defined by the user. The overall score that can be given is 100 percentage points which can be distributed among the chosen indicators based on the preferred weighting scheme, see **Table 2**. Several methods exist to assess the weighting scheme of stakeholders, such as expert consultation, discrete choice analysis, etc. The chosen weighting values will be connected to the net flows (see Sections 3.8 and 3.9).

Table 2: Weighting scheme.

Indicators	Weight
GHG	0.33
LMC	0.33
FWP	0.34

Results:

For users who do not have any experience

Once all parameters are chosen, the Excel file runs its iterations automatically (enter any random number => activates the Monte Carlo simulation) and provides the results, see **Figure 2**. This is perfect for users who immediately want to use the tool without diving into the internal mechanism and calculations of the stochastic MCDA, and are fine with 4 products and 3 indicators.

Figure 2: Rank acceptability indices for products A, B, C and D. The x-axis shows the rank position, and the y-axis, the rank acceptability (in percentage) for each product for every rank.

Figure 3 illustrates the probabilities of being ranked first, second, third, and fourth for each product according to the assessment.

Figure 3: Ranking based on products based on probability calculation of 1000 iterations.

For experienced users:

For those who want to further understand, adjust, extend, and tailor-made the tool according to the condition of their products, it is advised to go over all the following worksheets (Section 3.3 – 3.9) and consult the guideline of Prado and Heijungs (2018) for further insights.

To extend the tool to more than 4 products and 3 indicators, additional columns need to be added. It is quite straightforward. To extend the structure in each worksheet, the user needs to copy and paste the columns, rows, and Excel-based equations. Hence, no further explanation is needed.

3.3 Products indicator value (h)

The first step is to calculate the difference (d_{ijk_r}) between alternative pairs (e.g. product A vs B) on a specific impact category (e.g. GHG emissions) for a pre-defined number of Monte Carlo iterations.

To do so, first, we need to calculate the randomized values for each alternative (h_{ij_r}) based on the parameters (*mean and sigma*) in 'Input parameters and results', see **Table 3**. The stochastic outcome of the alternatives A, B, C and D are based on the indicator GHG for 1000 iterations r .

Table 3: Randomized values for each alternative (h_{ij_r}).

Products indicator value (h)						
Monte Carlo generator						
Trial (r)	Product A			Product B		
	h_GHG(A)r	h_LMC(A)r	h_FWP(A)r	h_GHG(B)r	h_LMC(B)r	h_FWP(B)r
1	8.88	60.68	-2.04	5.14	48.60	-1.75
2	8.78	68.05	-2.20	5.26	65.43	-1.80
3	7.93	79.75	-1.75	4.79	60.39	-2.00

3.4. Pairwise difference (d)

Next, the pairwise difference is calculated. For instance, the difference between product A and B value for iteration $r = 1$ ($8.88 - 5.14 = 3.74$) is calculated using the following **Equation 1**:

$$d_{ijk_r} = h_{ij_r} - h_{ik_r} \quad (i = 1, \dots, m; j, k = 1, \dots, n; r = 1, \dots, R) \quad (1)$$

The result is illustrated in **Table 4**:

Table 4: Pairwise differences.

Pairwise difference (d)				
Trial (r)	d_GHG(AB)r	d_GHG(AC)r	d_GHG(AD)r	d_GHG(BC)r
1	3.74	-0.38	4.40	-4.12
2	3.52	-0.35	3.77	-3.87
3	3.14	-1.41	2.85	-4.55

3.5. Thresholds

In the next step, the thresholds are calculated. Thresholds are established criteria for decision-making based on the preferences and priorities of the user. Prado and Heijungs (2018) considered an automatic uncertainty-generated threshold to avoid subjective information, using the following **Equations 2, 3, and 4**:

$$P_i = \frac{-1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n S_{ij} \quad (i = 1, \dots, m) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_i = \frac{1}{2} P_i \quad (i = 1, \dots, m) \quad (3)$$

$$S_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R-1} + \sum_{r=1}^R (h_{ijr} - \bar{h}_{ij})^2} \quad (i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n) \quad (4)$$

The preference threshold (P_i) and indifference threshold (Q_i) are generated based on $r = 1000$ (iterations), illustrated in **Table 5**:

Table 5: Preference threshold (P_i) and indifference threshold (Q_i).

Preference	Indifference
P_GHG	Q_GHG
-0.66	-0.33

For P_i , the threshold level is the average of all standard deviation (s) and for Q_i , it is P_i divided by 2.

3.6. Outranking score (Θ_{ijkR})

In the next step, the relative performance of alternatives is measured using the outranking score Θ_{ijkR} . These values range between 0 to 1, defined by **Equation 5** and visualized in **Figure 4**:

$$\theta_{ijkR} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d_{ijkR} \geq Q_i \text{ (indifference)} \\ 1 & \text{if } d_{ijkR} \leq P_i \text{ (complete preference)} \\ \frac{Q_i - d_{ijkR}}{Q_i - P_i} & \text{if } P_i \leq d_{ijkR} \leq Q_i \text{ (partial preference)} \end{cases} \quad (i = 1, \dots, m; j, k = 1, \dots, n; r = 1, \dots, R) \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: Outranking preference function where lower environmental impact is preferred. Based on Prado and Heijungs (2018).

Indifference ($\Theta_{ijk} = 0$)

If the first condition is met, then the difference between products is negligible. Hence, there is not sufficient evidence of the superiority of a product. This is called a tie. Hence, the number zero is given, see **Table 6**:

Table 6: Indifference ($\Theta_{ijk} = 0$).

theta_GHG(AD)r
0

Partial preference ($0 < \Theta_{ijk} < 1$)

If the third condition of the equation is met, then the outranking score will be between $0 < \Theta_{ijk} < 1$, see **Table 7**:

Table 7: Partial preference ($0 < \Theta_{ijk} < 1$).

theta_GHG(AC)r
-0.146

Complete preference ($\Theta_{ijk} = 1$)

To give an example: The outranking score theta '1' for GHG between product A and B shows that product B performs better than product A. Hence, the value 1 is given, see **Table 8**:

Table 8: Complete preference ($\Theta_{ijk} = 1$).

theta_GHG(BA)r
1

In this case, lower values (e.g. GHG emissions) are preferred over higher values. Product B (5.14) performs better than product A (8.88), resulting in $d = -3.74$. Looking at the equation above, the pairwise comparison between products A and B fulfils the second condition of the equation, the requirement of threshold P (-0.66) of having a lower value. Hence, it means that Product B is completely preferable over product A, which results in the number '1'.

3.7. Net flows (π)

For each pairwise comparison, there are two ways to compare: (i) product A with B and (ii) product B with A, which creates positive and negative values. For instance, positive value indicates how much product A outperforms product B, and negative values indicate how much product A is outperformed by product B. Hence, both values need to be considered by using **Equation 6**:

$$\pi_{ijr} = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ k \neq j}}^n (\theta_{ijk} - \theta_{ikj}) \quad (i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n, r = 1, \dots, R) \quad (6)$$

Considering the following values in worksheet ‘Outranking score (theta),...

- for $\Theta_{XAB} = 0$
- and $\Theta_{XBA} = 1$
- and $\Theta_{XAC} = -0.146$
- and $\Theta_{XCA} = 0$
- and $\Theta_{XAD} = 0$
- and $\Theta_{XDA} = 1$

... the number **-2.146** = $((0-1)+(-0.146+0)+(0-1))$ is calculated, shown in **Table 9**:

Table 9: Outranking score.

Net flows (π)				
Trial (r)	pi_GHG(A)r	pi_LMC(A)r	pi_FWP(A)r	pi_GHG(B)r
1	-2.146721757	2.978084426	-1.853278243	1.021915574
2	-2.055201038	2	-1.944798962	2
3	-1	2	-3	2

Note that this number is important to calculate the overall score in the worksheet ‘Overall score’.

3.8. Weights (w)

To prioritize the importance of impacts in the entire evaluation, a weighting scheme needs to be applied (see Prado and Heijungs (2018)). It reflects the relative importance of impacts according to the user’s chosen values and does not depend on the performance of the alternatives.

The predefined weighting scheme (in Section 3.2) is linked to each iteration, see **Table 10**:

Table 10: Sum of pre-defined weights for 10 iterations.

Weights (w)			
Trial (r)	w_GHG	w_LMC	w_FWP
1	0.330	0.330	0.340
2	0.330	0.330	0.340
3	0.330	0.330	0.340

3.9. Overall score (z) and rank (R)

The overall score is calculated by **Equation 7**:

$$z_{jr} = \sum_{i=1}^m w_{ir} * \pi_{ijr} \quad (j = 1, \dots, n, r = 1, \dots, R) \quad (7)$$

where the weights (w_{ir}) are multiplied by the net flows (π_{ijr}), creating a ranking for each of the 1000 iterations (**Table 11**):

Table 11: Overall score for 1000 iterations.

Trial (r)	Overall score				Rank (r)			
	z_Ar	z_Br	z_Cr	z_Dr	Product A	Product B	Product C	Product D
1	-0.65	2.00	-1.65	0.30	3	1	4	2
2	0.02	0.15	-1.30	1.13	3	2	4	1
3	-1.21	1.82	-1.41	0.80	3	1	4	2

Lastly, in 'Rank (R)', the result of the stochastic MCDA is calculated. All rankings of 1000 iterations are accounted for (see **Table 12**), resulting in the probability distribution, illustrated in **Figure 5**.

Table 12: Ranking of Product A, B, C, and D based on the Indicators GHG, LMC, and FWP.

		Alternatives			
		Product A	Product B	Product C	Product D
		R_A	R_B	R_C	R_D
Rank position	1	11	627	0	354
	2	61	334	31	565
	3	553	25	347	67
	4	369	5	615	4

Figure 5: Rank acceptability indices for products A, B, C and D. The x-axis shows the rank position, and the y-axis, the rank acceptability (in percentage points) for each product for every rank.

Interpretation:

Based on the assessment, the following ranking is calculated: product B (approx. 62%, blue) => D (approx. 57%, orange), => A (approx. 55%, green), => and C (approx. 65%, yellow). Currently, all indicators have the same priority (33.33%). Products B and D are prioritised over A and C due to the lower impacts in GHG and LMC. However, products A and B have better FWP values compared to C and D. Product B is prioritised over B due to the greater outcome in FWP.

Example product B:

4 alternatives (A, B, C, and D) are assessed based on three indicators (GHG, LMC, and FWP) under an equal weighting scheme (33% each) over 1000 iterations. Taking Product B as an example, the probability of being ranked Nr. 1 is 62%, based on the three indicators, the equal weighting scheme, and 1000 iterations. This also means that among 1000 iterations,

620 product B was ranked first. Following the same logic, 330 iterations ranked second, 40 times third, and only 3 times fourth.

4. References

- Eickhout, B., 2012. A strategy for a bio-based economy. Green New Deal Series, 9, https://gef.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/A_strategy_for_a_bio-based_economy.pdf (accessed 30 January 2024).
- European Commission, 2012. Innovating for Sustainable Growth: A bioeconomy for Europe. https://www.ecsite.eu/sites/default/files/201202_innovating_sustainable_growth_en.pdf (accessed 30 January 2024).
- European Commission, 2018. A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment : updated bioeconomy strategy. Publications Office.
- European Commission, 2019. The European Green Deal. Communicaton from the commission to the European parliament, The European council, the council, The European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF (accessed 30 January 2024).
- Fritsche, U., Iriarte, L., 2014. Sustainability Criteria and Indicators for the Bio-Based Economy in Europe: State of Discussion and Way Forward. *Energies* 7, 6825–6836. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en7116825>.
- Hertwich, E.G., Hammitt, J.K., 2001. A decision-analytic framework for impact assessment part I: LCA and decision analysis. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02977588>.
- Laurin, L., Amor, B., Bachmann, T.M., Bare, J., Koffler, C., Genest, S., Preiss, P., Pierce, J., Satterfield, B., Vigon, B., 2016. Life cycle assessment capacity roadmap (section 1): decision-making support using LCA. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 21, 443–447. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1031-y>.
- Leal-Millan, A., Peris-Ortiz, M., Leal-Rodríguez, A.L., 2018. Sustainability in Innovation and Entrepreneurship. Springer International Publishing, Cham.
- Prado-Lopez, V., Heijungs, R., 2018. Implementation of stochastic multi-attribute analysis (SMAA) in comparative environmental assessments. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 109, 223–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.08.021>.
- Prado-Lopez, V., Seager, T.P., Chester, M., Laurin, L., Bernardo, M., Tylock, S., 2014. Stochastic multi-attribute analysis (SMAA) as an interpretation method for comparative life-cycle assessment (LCA). *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 19, 405–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-013-0641-x>.
- United Nations, 2015. Transforming our world: the 2030 agenda for sustainable development. <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N15/291/89/PDF/N1529189.pdf?OpenElement> (accessed 30 January 2024).
- Van Schoubroeck, S., Thomassen, G., van Passel, S., Malina, R., Springael, J., Lizin, S., Venditti, R.A., Yao, Y., van Dael, M., 2021. An integrated techno-sustainability assessment (TSA) framework for emerging technologies. *Green Chem.* 23, 1700–1715. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1gc00036e>.
- Van Schoubroeck, S., van Dael, M., van Passel, S., Malina, R., 2018. A review of sustainability indicators for biobased chemicals. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 94, 115–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.06.007>.
- Wang, J.-J., Jing, Y.-Y., Zhang, C.-F., Zhao, J.-H., 2009. Review on multi-criteria decision analysis aid in sustainable energy decision-making. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 13, 2263–2278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.06.021>.